

IMPLEMENTATION OF GOVERNOR OF NORTH MALUKU REGULATION NO. 19 OF 2020: PROVISION OF ADDITIONAL INCOME FOR CIVIL SERVANTS WITHIN THE REGIONAL SECRETARIAT OF NORTH MALUKU PROVINCE FISCAL YEAR 2021

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Abstract

This research aims to know and analyze the implementation of governor regulation number 19 of 2020 regarding additional income for civil servants in North Maluku Province in the 2021 fiscal year. The type of research is qualitative descriptive research (field) with primary and secondary data sources while collecting data through observation, interview, and documentation. Based on the result of this research, the implementation of Governor Regulation number 19 of 2021 about additional income provision payment for government employees within the regional secretariat of North Maluku Province has not been implemented optimally because there are still two months in the payment process that have not been paid in the 2021 fiscal year, namely November and December. Policy implementers, especially BKD, have communicated to employees to employees through socialization activities payment mechanism by Governor Regulation No. 19/2021. Resource dimensions: employee human resources and finance/budget are by Governor Regulation No. 19/2021. The number of human resources employees at the regional secretariat is 439 people. The TPP budget each year is sourced from the Provincial APBD. The dimensions of disposition/division of tasks, organizational structure, and employee attitudes have also been stated in Governor Regulation (Pergub) number 36 of 2021 and employee performance target (SKP).

Keywords: Implementation, Governor Regulation, Additional Income for the Employee.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are vital assets for organizations because their role in strategy implementation is vital as the implementing subject of the organization's strategy. Human resources are the people in the organization directly related to their work. Having qualified and professional human resources is an organization's expectation. Organizations with this will be able to achieve optimal performance as desired by the organization, both by individual employees and work groups (teamwork), so that goals can be achieved and realized.

Good apparatus performance is also needed for good performance from government organizations. Generally, employee performance can be known through informal assessments, such as comments or good or bad judgments from superiors and subordinates. However, it would be more relevant if the performance assessment were also measured through formal and structured (measurable) assessments conducted by the agency itself or other competent agencies/agencies/ministries/institutions.

Suppose the performance appraisal is carried out and refers to continuous formal measurement. In that case, the assessment is more complete and detailed because the characteristics related to work, work standards, behavior, work results, and even the employee's absenteeism rate can be assessed.

In line with the performance issues of the state civil apparatus, as described above, the aspect that needs to be considered is the welfare of the state civil apparatus. Welfare is directly related to providing salaries/incentives for state civil servants who work wholeheartedly and continuously improve their performance.

The provision of welfare for the state civil apparatus within North Maluku Province has been outlined in Governor Regulation 19 of 2020 concerning the Provision of Additional Civil Servant Income, commonly called TPP. In the Provisions of Article 1 paragraph (9) of the North Maluku Governor Regulation Number 19 of 2020 concerning the Provision of Additional Income for Civil Servants within the Government of North Maluku Province for the 2021 Budget Year, which previously read: Additional Employee Income, from now on abbreviated as TPP, is income received by employees outside of salaries and other legal allowances in the context of improving welfare given based on work performance and work behavior.

Furthermore, Article 4 explains that TPP is given based on the following criteria: workload, work achievement, place of duty, working conditions, professional scarcity, and other objective considerations.

To the proposed regulation of the Governor of North Maluku, the provision of additional employee income (TPP) must be based on the Employee Performance Targets Report (SKP), and each employee must compile Employee Performance Targets (SKP). The Employee Performance Targets consist of Annual and Monthly Employee Performance Targets. The North Maluku Governor Regulation explains that the provision of TPP to the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is carried out monthly. Still, until 2022, from the beginning of January to June, it has not been disbursed/given to ASN.

In addition, from July to December 2022, the payment process has not been fully paid to ASN. Of course, this is a problem for the regional government of North Maluku Province to make lessons learned so that the Employee Income Supplement budget is immediately disbursed and immediately given to ASNs within North Maluku Province as soon as possible.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study used descriptive qualitative (field) research to provide an overview (description) of an institution's nature, circumstances, events, or activities and then describe the problems studied through several related indicators.

The descriptive qualitative method is used to describe the facts of the phenomena subjectively/objectively, which becomes the researcher's problem and the form of field survey research with Descriptive research type. Bogdan and Taylor (Moleong, 2010: 4). In a qualitative approach, researchers try to observe and reveal the reality in the field.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Public Policy Theory

According to Carl Friedrich (in Wahab, 1991: 13), policy is defined as an action that leads to goals proposed by a person, group, or government in a particular environment in connection with certain obstacles while looking for opportunities to achieve goals or realize targets, which is fantastic. Meanwhile, James Anderson in Nurcholis (2005) states that policy is an action with a purpose carried out by an actor or several actors to solve a problem.

Thomas R. Dye (1975:1) states "whatever government chooses to do or not to do", Public Policy is whatever the government chooses to do or not to do. Dye went on to say that if the government chooses to do something, it must have a purpose. Public policy must include all government actions so that it is not merely a statement of the government's or government officials' wishes. What the government does not do is also public policy because it has the same significant impact as something it does. What is done and what is not are related to one goal as an essential policy component. Robert Eyestone, in *The Threads of Public Policy* (1971) (in Agustino 2008), defines public policy as "the relationship between government units and their environment". The meaning can include almost all elements in the context of the country. Heinz Eulau and Kenneth Prewitt (1973:265), in their perspective, define public policy as "'fixed decisions' which are characterized by consistency and repetition (repetition) of the behavior of those who make and of those who comply with these decisions."

Policy Implementation Theory

In principle, policy implementation is a way for a policy to achieve its goals, nothing more or less. There are two steps available to implement public policy, namely, implementing it directly in the form of programs or through the formulation of derivative policies or derivatives of these policies. Public policy in the form of laws or regional regulations is a type of policy that requires explanatory public policies or is often termed implementing regulations. Public policies that can be directly operationalized include Presidential Decrees, Presidential Instructions, Ministerial Decrees, Regional Head Decrees, Service Head Decrees, and others (Nugroho, 2011:618-619). Soleman et al. (2021) Implementation changes, how change occurs, and how the possibility of change can arise; it is also a study of the microstructure of political life.

Meanwhile, according to Grindle (1980), policy implementation is not just related to translating political decisions into routine procedures through bureaucratic channels. Still, more than that, it concerns issues of conflict, decisions, and who gets the benefits. What is a policy?

Implementation Model According to Edward III, as quoted by Subarsono (2011:90-92), the following is described. Communication is a variable that becomes a benchmark for success in implementing a policy by requiring that someone implementing the policy can know what things they must do, as well as having an understanding of the goals and objectives of the policy that must be transmitted to the target group to minimize implementation distortion. All personnel must accept implementation, and the intent and objectives of the policy must be

clearly and accurately understood. Three indicators can be used to measure the success of this aspect of communication, namely,

- 1) Transmission, good communication distribution will produce good implementation results. Often, what happens in this transmission process is a misunderstanding. This happens because the implementation communication has gone through several levels of bureaucracy, so what is expected is distorted along the way;
- 2) Clarity of information: the communication or information received by policy implementers must be clear and not confusing. Clarity of policy information does not always hinder policy implementation, where at a certain level, implementers need flexibility, which will distort the goals to be achieved by the policy that has been established; and
- 3) Consistency of the information conveyed, namely orders or information given in implementing a communication must be clear and consistent to be implemented and carried out. If the orders given frequently change, it can confuse implementers in the field.

Resource components include the number of staff, the expertise of the implementers, relevant and sufficient information to implement policies and the fulfillment of relevant resources in implementing the program, the existence of authority that guarantees that the program can be directed as expected, and the existence of supporting facilities, which can be used to carry out program activities such as funds, facilities, and infrastructure. Inadequate human resources (number and ability) result in the program being unable to be implemented perfectly because they cannot carry out supervision properly. If the number of staff implementing the policy is limited, then what must be done is to increase the skills/ability of the implementers to carry out the program. For this reason, there is a need for good HR management to improve program performance.

Information is an essential resource for policy implementers. There are two forms of information regarding how to complete policies/programs. Implementers must know what actions must be taken, and there must be information about data supporting compliance with government regulations and laws. Other resources that are also important are the authority to determine the programs carried out and the authority to spend/manage finances, whether providing money, procuring staff, or procuring supervisors. The facilities must be met to implement policies/programs, such as offices, equipment, and sufficient funds.

Disposition is the implementer's character and characteristics, such as commitment, honesty, and democracy. One of the factors that influences the effectiveness of policy implementation is the attitude of the implementer. If implementers agree with parts of the policy's content, they will implement it happily. However, if their views differ from those of policymakers, the implementation process will experience many problems.

Support from leadership greatly influences program implementation in achieving goals effectively and efficiently. The manifestation of this leadership support is placing policy as a

program priority, placing implementers with people who support the program, and showing a balance of the region, religion, ethnicity, gender, and other democratic characteristics. Apart from that, providing sufficient funds to provide incentives for program implementers so that they support and work totally in implementing policies/programs.

The bureaucratic structure in implementing policies has a significant influence on policy implementation. Implementing a policy cannot be separated from the bureaucratic structure. Bureaucratic structure is the characteristics, norms, and relationship patterns that occur repeatedly in executive bodies with potential and actual relationships with what they have in implementing policies.

Grandle (in Wahab 1997) explains that policy implementation is not just related to translating political decisions into routine procedures through bureaucratic channels. Still, more than that, it involves conflicting decisions about who gets a policy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Implementation of North Maluku Governor Regulation Number 19 of 2020

Providing additional employee income is a form of appreciation to Civil Servants (PNS) or State Civil Apparatus (ASN), which has a legal basis, guidelines, criteria, and measurable assessment indicators to increase discipline, motivation, performance, and welfare of Civil Servants (PNS) or State Civil Apparatus within the North Maluku Provincial Government. Additional employee income, abbreviated as TPP, is income received by employees outside of salary and other legal allowances to improve welfare, which is given based on work performance and work behavior.

Job Achievement, Target, and Work Behavior are essential for providing additional employee income (TPP). The purposes of these three references include:

- 1) Performance Achievements are performance plans and targets that employees must achieve within an assessment period that are real and can be measured and agreed upon by employees and their superiors;
- 2) Target is the amount of workload that will be achieved from each implementation of position duties; and
- 3) Work Behavior is any behavior, attitude or action carried out by an employee or not doing something that the provisions of laws and regulations should do.

The assessment process for the three references mentioned above is contained in the Employee Performance Targets. Employee Performance Targets (SKP) are work plans and targets to be achieved by a Civil Servant (PNS), which must be achieved every year. Based on the report from the Employee Performance Targets (SKP) for each Civil Servant, Additional Employee Income (TPP) is provided based on Position Class for each Civil Servant or State Civil Apparatus (ASN) within the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province. From Governor's Regulation Number 19 of 2020, the TPP amount is explained based on the clusters of each ASN as in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Amount of Additional Employee Income Based on Position Class 2020

Position Class	Income Based (IDR)
16	14,748,000
15	11,714,400
14	8,918,000
13	8,004,000
12	6,400,000
11	4,948,000
10	4,304,000
9	3,744,000
8	3,009,200
7	2,653,200
6	2,305,600
5	1,922,800
4	1,139,600
3	941,600
2	778,800
1	616,000

Data Source: PERGUB No. 19/2020

Table 2: Amount of Additional Employee Income Based on Position Class for OPD-TAPD and Inspectorate 2020

Position Class	Income Based (IDR)	Additional for OPD-TAPD (IDR)	Additional for Inspectorate (IDR)
16	14,748,000	-	-
15	11,714,400	13,178,700	13,764,420
14	8,918,000	10,032,750	10,478,650
13	8,004,000	9,004,500	9,404,700
12	6,400,000	7,200,000	7,520,000
11	4,948,000	5,566,500	5,813,900
10	4,304,000	4,842,000	5,057,200
9	3,744,000	4,212,000	4,399,200
8	3,009,200	3,385,350	3,535,810
7	2,653,200	2,984,850	3,117,510
6	2,305,600	2,593,800	2,709,080
5	1,922,800	2,163,150	2,259,290
4	1,139,600	1,282,050	1,339,030
3	941,600	1,059,300	1,106,380
2	778,800	876,150	915,090
1	616,000	693,000	723,800

Data Source: PERGUB No. 19/2020

The stages of the implementation process for providing and paying Additional Employee Income (TPP) for PNS/ASN must go through a payment mechanism. It is by Article 22 of the North Maluku Gubernatorial Regulation that the results of work behavior and work performance are recapitulated every month by

- a) Leadership Administration at the Regional Secretariat for the Regional Secretary, Assistant Regional Secretary, and Governor's Expert Staff;
- b) Subdivision in charge of personnel duties for Regional Apparatus; and
- c) Subdivision of Administration for the Bureau. This Additional Employee Income (TPP) helps employees/ASNs by increasing employee/ASN income monthly.

From the findings, the implementation of North Maluku Governor Regulation Number 19 of 2020 for Payment of TPP for Employees/ASN for the 2021 Fiscal Year has indeed been implemented. However, there are still 2 (months), namely November and December, that must be paid in the 2023 Fiscal Year. (TPP) for employees/ASN in North Maluku Province in general and more specifically in the Regional Secretariat (Setda), due to several reasons, namely:

- 1) Regional Apparatus Organizations (OPD) have not submitted a TPP, because ASN has not fully completed the SKP;
- 2) The budget allocated for TPP is not sufficient for one fiscal year; and
- 3) For the beginning of the year, the APBD implementation process must wait for the evaluation results from the Ministry of Home Affairs so that APBD implementation for the beginning of the year often starts in February. So, the TPP payment at the beginning of the year is always delayed to the following month.

Communication Dimensions

Communication is carried out through the Socialization of North Maluku Governor's Regulations (PERGUB) regarding procedures for creating monthly Employee Performance Targets (SKP); the activity is carried out by the Regional Civil Service Agency (BKD). The BKD constantly socializes the North Maluku Governor's Regulations (PERGUB) to regional apparatus organizations within the North Maluku Provincial Government and the North Maluku Province Regional Secretariat (Setda).

Focus on socialization activities, namely, understanding ASN regarding the reporting of Employee Performance Targets (ASN) that employees/ASN must make. This socialization activity was carried out directly; the ASN carefully followed the socialization carried out by the BKD. In the socialization activity, the BKD conveyed several contents from North Maluku Governor Regulation Number 19 of 2020 concerning the provision of additional employee income for civil servants/ASN, including Criteria and Determination of the Amount of TPP; ASN Working Days and Hours; Preparation of Employee Work Targets (SKP); Absence; TPP assessment; Termination of TPP Payments and Cuts; and TPP Payment Mechanism.

Human and Financial Resources Dimensions

This resource component includes the number of staff, expertise of implementers, relevant and sufficient information to implement policies, and the fulfillment of relevant resources in program implementation. Inadequate human resources (number and capacity) result in the program being unable to be implemented significantly because they cannot carry out supervision properly. If the number of staff implementing the policy is limited, then what must be done is to increase the skills/ability of the implementers to carry out the program. For this reason, there is a need for good HR management to improve program performance.

Within the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province, human resources are adequate in quantity and quality. The resources for apparatus (HR)/employees/ASN at the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province are pretty adequate (quantity and quality) because the number of employees/ASN is 439 people spread across the Regional Secretariat and 9 (Nine) Bureaus at the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province. The Human Resources (HR) number and capabilities at the Regional Secretariat (Setda) of North Maluku Province are in Table 3. Based on Table 3, it can be explained that the majority of employees' educational levels based on the average level of education have a Bachelor's degree a total of 269 people, a high school education of 99 people, a Master's level education of 39 people, a Diploma 4 (D-IV) education of 15 people, 13 have a Diploma 3 (D-III) education, and 1 has the lowest elementary school (SD) education. So, the total number of employees/human resources at the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province is 439 people. For employees/ASNs, human resources based on the rank level within the Regional Secretariat (Setda) of North Maluku Province can be seen in Table 4.

Table 3: Regional Secretariat Human Resources based Education Level

Units	Educational Composition								
	Primary School	Junior High School	Senior High School	Diploma 3	Diploma 4	Bachelor	Master	Doctoral	Amount
The regional Secretariat	0	0	1	0	1	25	6	0	33
Bureau of Government and Regional Autonomy	1	0	6	0	5	17	6	0	35
People's Welfare Bureau	0	0	11	1	1	23	1	0	37
Legal Bureau	0	0	7	0	0	22	7	0	36
Economic Bureau	0	0	7	0	0	29	4	1	41
Goods and Services Procurement Bureau	0	0	5	0	2	39	5	0	51
General Bureau	0	1	41	8	3	49	2	0	104
Organization Bureau	0	0	7	2	1	26	3	0	39
Biro Administrasi Pembangunan	0	0	3	0	0	14	2	0	19
Leadership Administration Bureau	0	1	11	2	2	25	3	0	44
Total	1	2	99	13	15	269	39	1	439

Source: North Maluku Province Regional Secretariat, 2023

Table 4: Regional Secretariat Human Resources based Rank Level

Units	Rank Levels													
	I/ D	II/ A	II/ B	II/ C	II/ D	III/ A	III/ B	III/ C	III/ D	IV/ A	IV/ B	IV/ C	IV/ D	IV/ E
The regional Secretariat	0	0	0	1	0	2	5	5	5	0	2	8	4	1
Bureau of Government and Regional Autonomy	0	0	0	0	1	6	4	6	10	5	2	1	0	0
People's Welfare Bureau	0	0	2	2	1	6	4	6	12	2	1	1	0	0
Legal Bureau	0	0	1	2	2	4	3	5	9	4	4	1	1	0
Economic Bureau	0	0	1	0	2	6	3	2	17	4	6	0	0	0
Goods and Services Procurement Bureau	0	1	1	0	0	8	5	13	17	5	1	0	0	0
General Bureau	1	0	4	8	16	25	10	16	18	3	2	1	0	0
Organization Bureau	0	1	1	1	2	2	8	13	6	1	3	0	1	0
Biro Administrasi Pembangunan	0	0	1	0	1	1	3	5	5	2	0	1	0	0
Leadership Administration Bureau	0	1	1	3	5	6	7	4	13	2	1	0	1	0
Total	1	3	12	17	30	66	52	75	112	28	22	13	7	1

Source: North Maluku Province Regional Secretariat, 2023

Based on Table 4, it can be explained that the majority of ASN rank levels are at rank III/d with a total of 112 people, rank III/c consists of 75 people, rank III/a consists of 66 people, rank III/b consists of 52 people, rank II/d consists of 30 people, rank IV/a consists of 28 people, rank IV/b consists of 22 people, rank II/c consists of 17 people. Furthermore, related finances/funds for the payment of Additional Employee Income (TPP) come from the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD) of North Maluku Province for the Fiscal Year 2020. The amount of TPP in each year is budgeted at IDR. 16,299,928,000,-. the entire TPP budget is paid directly to employees/ASN in non-cash form or via transfer to each employee.

Dimensions of Disposition/Division of Tasks

The Governor of North Maluku Province has incentivized employees/ASNs within the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province to carry out their duties by providing Additional Employee Income (TPP). TPP is part of incentives to increase and motivate employees to work according to the tasks they have been given.

The distribution of employee duties at the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province has so far been carried out concerning the regulations contained in Article 4 in the Regulation of the Governor of North Maluku Number 36 of 2021 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province, the entire series of tasks at the Regional Secretariat It has been explained in detail in the Gubernatorial Regulation. Meanwhile, the attitude of employees/ASNs within the Regional Secretariat is quite good because all actions, behavior, and attitudes of employees/ASNs are assessed directly on the Employee Performance Targets (SKP). That is why employees/ASNs always show a good attitude and report their performance in SKP, which is then assessed to be given monthly TPP.

Structure Dimensions

The final dimension from Edward III's view is that the bureaucratic or organizational structure that implements policies influences policy implementation. Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) and fragmentation are essential in an organizational structure in implementing policies. Suppose the organizational structure created tends to be long and complicated. In that case, this will result in weak implementation monitoring and can give rise to red tape, namely complicated and complex bureaucracy, causing organizational activities to run inflexibly and ineffectively.

The principal organizational structure of the Regional Secretariat has been regulated in North Maluku Governor Regulation Number 36 of 2021. The organizational structure of the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province has been regulated in Gubernatorial Regulation Number 36/2021 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province. The organizational structure of the Regional Secretariat can be explained as follows:

- a) Regional Secretary;
- b) Governor's Expert Staff for Government, Law and Politics;
- c) Governor's Expert Staff for Economics, Finance and Development;
- d) Governor's Expert Staff for Social Affairs and Human Resources;
- e) Assistant for Government and People's Welfare, in charge of 2 bureaus, namely:
 - 1) Government Bureau;
 - 2) People's Welfare Bureau;
 - 3) Legal Bureau;

- f) Assistant for Economics and Development, overseeing:
- 1) Economic Bureau;
 - 2) Goods and Services Procurement Bureau;
 - 3) Development Administration Bureau;
- g) General Administration Assistant, in charge of 3 bureaus, namely:
- 1) Organization Bureau
 - 2) General Bureau;
 - 3) Leadership Administration Bureau;

Meanwhile, the basis of the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) in implementing the provision of TPP for employees within the Regional Secretariat of North Maluku Province is always guided by Governor's Regulation Number 19/2021 concerning Providing Additional Employee Income (TPP) while the technical instructions for implementing TPP have been regulated in the Regulation of the Governor of North Maluku, including those contained in Articles 22 to 24.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Implementing Governor Regulation No.19/2021 concerning TPP payments has not been optimal because the payment process is still two months unpaid in the 2021 budget year, namely November and December.
2. Policy implementers, especially BKD, have carried out the communication dimension through outreach activities to employees regarding the TPP payment mechanism by Governor Regulation No.19/2021.
3. Resource dimensions: Employee human resources and finance/budget are by Governor Regulation No.19/2021. The number of human resources employees at the Regional Secretariat is 439 people, and the annual TPP budget comes from the Provincial APBD; the dimensions of disposition/division of tasks, organizational structure, and employee attitudes are stated in Governor Regulation (Pergub) Number 36 of 2021 and Employee Performance Targets (SKP).

SUGGESTIONS

1. The North Maluku provincial government must allocate the TPP budget by the applicable Gubernatorial Regulations and pay it every 12 months and not postpone payments to the next fiscal year;
2. The Regional Secretary (Sekda) must carefully control TPP payments every month so that the TPP payment process to employees can run smoothly;

3. Employees/ASNs must continue to improve their performance and behavior and commit to carrying out their duties by their primary duties and functions.

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